

Fiscal Decentralization and Economic Growth in Pakistan: An ARDL Approach¹

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Abstract

The relationship between fiscal decentralization and economic growth is widely debated in literature; however, there have been limited attempts to systematically verify this relationship. By using the autoregressive distributed lag model framework, an attempt is made to identify the relationship using the case of Pakistan. This study finds that (at least for Pakistan) fiscal decentralization is positively related to economic growth. Such findings imply that fiscal decentralization could be used as a vehicle to achieve long-term economic growth in the case of Pakistan. However, it is also suggested that factors such as over-dependence of provincial governments on the central government, undefined functional and tax responsibilities, and a limited and unaffected tax base for provincial and local governments may undermine the full benefits of fiscal decentralization.

Key Words: Fiscal Decentralization, Economic Growth, ARDL method

INTRODUCTION

The process of decentralization continues to be widely debated in literature. Most countries have attempted to challenge the monopoly of power held by central governments in the decision-making process that motivates central governments to transfer the authority of performing certain functions by lower level.

Fiscal decentralization (FD), transfers fiscal assignments from the central government to lower level of governments,² and is that the heart of any devolutionary exercise. Without the appropriate degree of FD no authority can be devolved. The basic concept involves the transfer of funds to sub-national governments according to their due share along with the authority and flexibility to spend the funds in regards to local priorities.

The main economic argument for FD is because it increases economic efficiency as sub-national governments have more information about the preferences and tastes of

constituents. Oates (1993) argued that when goods and services are provided to local constituents in accordance with their tastes and preferences (as compared to centrally determined uniform levels) it increases social welfare. The process of FD also leads to an improvement in governance, as the allotment of increased authority and flexibility for spending funds makes local governments fully responsible to the judicious and cost effective utilization of funds. It also makes the local government accountable for their performance, especially in relation to service delivery. An adequate degree of FD is a necessary pre-requisite for the success of the local government system; however, some researchers disagree with this proposition.³ For example, Tanzi (1995) illustrated that taxpayers do not generally have sufficient political power or information to place pressure on local policymakers for efficient decision-making. He further illustrated that (particularly in developing countries), state or local politicians are generally more corrupt than several ones. As a result of these situations or circumstances, the policy decision of FD may have less than optimal result.

Prior to independence in Pakistan,⁴ the devolutionary reforms were started by non-representative regimes of the British. Later, these reforms were carried out by three military regimes.⁵ However, it has been learned that the devolutionary reforms implemented by military regimes involve the transfer of certain powers and functions from provinces⁶ to local governments; however, they often strengthened the central government.

The decentralization process involves the transfer of a large number of functions and powers⁷ from central to provincial and from provincial to local governments. However, in the case of Pakistan, before the promulgation of the *Local Government Ordinance, 2001* and introduction of *Legal Framework Order, 2002* the functions and powers are generally allocated in the *Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, 1973* to only Federal and Provincial tiers of government. There is a need to decentralize some functions and powers to the sub-national level. The last military regime in early 2000 (following the norms of other two military regimes), started devolutionary exercise wherein inter-alia, local governments have been recognized as a third or lower tier. This reform transfers sufficient fiscal powers to the lower tiers of government.

Theoretical models of FD provide arguments for its relationship with economic growth; however, its direction is less clear-cut. One theory argued that FD is positively related with economic growth through improved supply of public goods by considering diverse local preferences and inter-jurisdictional competition among sub-national governments that provides incentives for product innovation that enhance consumers as well as producers efficiency. A second theory argued that it is negatively related with economic growth as inter-jurisdictional tax competition leads to higher regional disparities and corruption that leads to undersupply of public goods. In addition, empirical validations for theoretical foundations are also ambiguous. For example, Xie et. al. (1999), Thie β en (2000) and Desai, et. al (2003) found a positive association while Davoodi and Zou (1998) and Zhang and Zou (1998) found a negative relationship between FD and economic growth. Empirical analysis provides an opportunity to determine the direction of this relationship for Pakistan as well as encourage the estimation of its impact on economic growth.

The main reason to analyze the case of Pakistan is that public finances in Pakistan are characterized by large

vertical fiscal imbalances between the federal and provincial governments due to highly skewed taxation powers towards the federal government and the related slow growth of provincial revenue. The recent move by Pakistan to provide more fiscal autonomy to the provinces motivated us to analyze whether the change in environment has improved the intended efficiency and economic growth. The present study is valuable for Pakistani policy makers and researchers as well as for countries whose government structure is similar to Pakistan.

The Present study is unique in the sense that previous studies generally used simple OLS techniques to evaluate relationships; however, present study uses a recently developed technique of an Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) to determine the long-run association between FD and economic growth. Further, limited studies have been made for the context of Pakistan. For example, Cheema and Mohmand (2003), Cheema et. al (2004) and Zaidi (2005) examined the process of decentralization in a historical context; Pasha and Pasha (2000) identified major issues of FD in relation to the devolution plan of 2000. Whereas, Malik et. al (2006) empirically examined this impact for Pakistan through the use of a simple OLS technique.

The reason to determine the relationship between FD and economic growth is three fold: First, the objective of any devolution exercise (particularly devolution of fiscal powers to the lower level) is to improve the efficiency in the resource allocation of the public sector that leads to economic growth. Second, it is one of the objectives of government to implement policies that augment income of the masses and last, measuring economic growth is easier than other indicators [Zhang and Zou (2001)].

The study progresses as follows: Section II reviewed empirical literature and briefly examines the decentralization process in Pakistan. Methodology, data descriptions and empirical results are explained in Section III. the last section is devoted to the conclusion and policy implications.

LITERATURE REVIEW: LINKING FISCAL DECENTRALIZATION TO ECONOMIC GROWTH

Analyzing causal links between FD and economic

growth is important as it provides a base to researchers and policy analysts to empirically validate causal links. The theory suggests that interdependence between FD and economic growth is multi-directional. This multi-directional causal relationship is summarized as follows.

Firstly, in the presence of heterogeneous preferences, it is relatively difficult to know about the taste and preference of each citizen. The provision of goods and services through the central government may be efficient; however, it is generally far from community preferences and higher transaction, information, and frustration costs may be the result. One possible way to minimize these costs is the decentralized provision of public services. Positive economic growth may be the result if decentralization attempts satisfy a consumer demand that enhance consumer efficiency. Secondly, a decentralized system may promote political and organizational innovations that can enforce competition among various authorities. Efficiency gains can be realized to the utilization of comparative advantages and by divisions of labor that promote economic growth. Thirdly, FD enforces inter-jurisdictional competition as well as makes local governments accountable to constituents that provide an incentive to government to innovate products. Producer efficiency in the supply of public goods increases; subsequently, economic growth is enhanced. Finally, inter-jurisdictional competition may lead to tax competitions that encourage regional disparity through the mobility of resources. The higher the mobility of resources, then lower the provision of public goods and services. The insufficient supply of public goods and services may lower economic growth. Thus, it is a very difficult a priori to say whether FD influences economic growth positively or negatively.

Tiebout (1956), Musgrave (1959) and Oates (1972) are considered pioneers in the examination of the theoretical role of FD in economic growth; however, the empirical work was started by Oates (1995). Probably the main reason for limited empirical studies before 1995 is the lack of data at the local government level. Since then, a number of studies quantified the impact by relating some measure of FD to economic growth.

Researchers and policy analysts have tried different approaches to link FD to economic growth. For example, in a sample of seventeen studies, nine studies have used cross-country data for this purpose. Oates (1995) used 40

countries panel data, Davoodi and Zou (1998) investigated 46 developing and OECD countries, Woller and Phillips (1998) analyzed 23 LDCs, Yilmaz (1999) examined 30 cross-countries by dividing them into federal (13) and unitary (17) countries, De Mello (2000) analyzed 17 OECD and 13 Non-OECD countries, Thie β en (2000 and 2003) studied all high-income OECD countries, Rodríguez-Pose and Krøijer (2008) studied 16 Central and Eastern Europe countries, and Baskaran and Feld (2009) analyzed 23 OECD countries panel data. Country specific analysis has also been made by some researchers. For instance, Zhang and Zou (1998) and Lin and Liu (2000) made the analysis for China, Xie et. al (1999) and Hammond and Tosun (2009) for the United States, Behnisch et. al (2001) for Germany, Zhang and Zou (2001) for China and India (same paper), Desai et. al (2003) for Russia, and Malik et. al (2006) for Pakistan.

The most important methodological problem is finding of an accurate measure for the prevailing degree of FD in the determination of the empirical relationship. This issue has been resolved in the literature by defining the term 'fiscal decentralization' in various ways. Most researchers defined this term as a share of sub-national government expenditure (or revenue) in total government expenditure (or revenue), net of inter-governmental transfers [see Oates (1995), Davoodi and Zou (1998), Woller and Phillips (1998), Xie et. al (1999), Yilmaz (1999), Thie β en (2000 and 2003) and Malik et. al (2006)]. Some studies purify the terminology further by subtracting defence and social securities/interest payments from consolidated expenditures, as these are exclusively under the domain of the federal/central government [see Woller and Phillips (1998) and Malik et. al (2006)]. In addition, some analyze various spending categories at the central level, such as education and science as one category and transport and communication other [see Behnisch et. al (2001)]. However, Zhang and Zou (1998 and 2001) defined this term as a ratio of consolidated provincial budgetary spending to central budgetary spending. Other proxies for FD used in the empirical research are the share of central government expenditures in total public expenditures [Behnisch et. al (2001)]; tax revenue retention and marginal retention rate of government revenue of sub-national governments [Desai et. al (2003) and Lin and Liu (2000) respectively]; and self-reliance ratio defined as own revenues of

sub-national governments as a share of their total revenue [Oates (1995) and Thieβ en (2000 and 2003)].

Researchers and policy analysts have paid many efforts for determining impact of FD on economic growth; however, the direction of this impact is unclear in some countries. In a sample of seventeen studies, nine have found a positive impact; three had either negative impacts, while others had mixed or inconclusive results. However, one study concluded that FD is unrelated with economic growth.⁸ The ambiguity of results motivates us to empirically examine the experience of Pakistan in this area. The following discussion analyzed the relative fiscal status of Pakistan and the extent of decentralization.

The public finances in Pakistan were not properly managed prior to 1999 as total expenditures existed beyond the available resources; subsequently, the overall fiscal deficit remains within the range of 5% to 10% of GDP. Further, the reliance of provincial revenue on federal government has substantially increased. This reliance was as high as 68% of total revenue in 1999. This may imply that the over-dependence of provincial resources on federal grants and shared taxes destroyed provincial fiscal autonomy. In 2001, the government adopted devolution policies that give some fiscal autonomy to provinces; subsequently, the composition of provincial revenue slightly improved.

The relative fiscal status of Pakistan's provincial governments as measured by FD-Exp⁹ and FD-Rev¹⁰ is depicted in Figure 1. It is observed that the share of provincial spending in total spending initially declined from 14.9% in 1979 to 11.9% in 1981. General Zia, in 1980, promulgated the *Local Government Ordinance* that delegated some fiscal power of the federal government to provincial governments. Because of the change in policy, the relative share of provinces increased from 11.9% to 19.6% in 1987. In 1988, the political governments took charge and reversed the policy of General Zia; subsequently, the relative share of provinces substantially decreased and reached the lowest share of 5.7% in 1997. General Musharraf again started devolution policies in 2000 and promulgated the *Local Government Ordinance*, 2001. By the promulgation of the Ordinance, certain functions that were earlier performed by the provinces such as primary and secondary education, water supply, drainage, and sewerage have been transferred to local governments. The series of FD-Rev showed almost the

same pattern as FD-Exp.

The Devolution Plan of 2001 delegates administrative and expenditure responsibilities to the local level. This changes the level of administrative decisions making authority and made them more accountable to their constituents. Table 1 shows the extent of FD.

Figure 1: Relative Fiscal Status of Pakistan's Provincial Governments

Source: Authors' calculation based on SBP Annual Reports various issues

Table 1. Expenditure by Different Levels of Government

(Rs. Billion)						
	2000-01	Share (%)	2005-06	Share (%)	2008-09	Share (%)
Federal	563.2	71.9	1006.7	63.8	2101.4	64.9
Provincial	180.0	23.0	371.7	23.6	897.5	27.7
Local	40.0	5.1	198.9	12.6	240.9	7.4
Total	783.2	100.0	1577.3	100.0	3239.8	100.0
As % of GDP						
Federal	13.4		13.0		16.0	
Provincial	4.3		4.8		6.9	
Local	1.0		2.6		1.8	
Total	18.7		20.4		24.7	

Source: Federal and Provincial Budget Estimates

During last military regime most fiscal powers were transferred from the federal to local governments that are evident from the increased share of local government expenditures. In 2001, the share of local governments was 5.1%; however, by 2006, it increased to 12.6%. Subsequent democratic governments¹¹ changed the policy and strengthened the fiscal autonomy of provincial governments by reversing fiscal powers that were earlier delegated to local governments; subsequently, the

provincial government share increased from 23.6% to 27.7%. The share of local governments has reduced from 12.6% to 7.4% by 2009; in addition, the present share is even higher than the share they had in 2001. We may conclude that military regimes used decentralization as a strategy to strengthen their governments.

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Three types of traditional growth regressions have been used in the literature: panel data regressions based on several period averages, pure cross-country regressions, and country specific regression. These analyses generally used OLS techniques and found a static relationship. The present study is based on country specific regression methodology and is an investigation of the dynamic relationships between the two variables of interest.

There are generally two ways to measure the degree of FD: expenditure approach and revenue approach. In first approach, the degree of FD has conventionally been measured as the share of sub-national government expenditures in the total government expenditures net of intergovernmental transfers.¹² In the revenue approach, FD is the ratio of sub-national government revenues to total government revenues.¹³ Following Davoodi and Zou (1998), Zhong and Zou (1998), and Xie et. al (1999), this study uses an expenditure approach as a measure of FD. Under this approach, FD has been defined as a share of consolidated provincial expenditures to total expenditures. Where consolidated expenditures are a sum of all four provinces expenditures, net of inter-governmental transfers; in addition, total expenditures are a sum of consolidated expenditures and federal expenditures. A ceteris paribus condition may exist in the following form: the higher the share of consolidated provincial government expenditures relative to total expenditures, then the higher the degree of FD.

Following Barro (1990) and Zhang and Zou (2001) an endogenous growth model that consists of a production function with several inputs is assumed: labour, physical capital, human capital, openness of economy, and FD.

$$Output = f(Labour, Capital, Education, Openness, Fiscal Decentralization, \dots\dots)$$

(+) (+) (+) (+) (+/-)

Using Cobb-Douglas production function the above function in term of explicit form can be written as:

$$(Y)_t = A_t (FD)_t^{\psi_1} (POP)_t^{\psi_2} (GFC)_t^{\psi_3} (MIDDLE)_t^{\psi_4} (OPEN)_t^{\psi_5} \dots\dots (1)$$

Where Y is real Gross Domestic Product at time 't'; A is the total factor productivity at time 't'; and FD is a measure of fiscal decentralization as defined above. The remaining variables are defined in the following paragraphs. For estimation purposes, equation (1) can be specified as follows:

$$\ln(Y)_t = \psi_0 + \psi_1 \ln(FD)_t + \psi_2 \ln(POP)_t + \psi_3 \ln(GFC)_t + \psi_4 \ln(MIDDLE)_t + \psi_5 \ln(OPEN)_t + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- POP = Population at time 't' (a proxy is used for labour);
- GFC = Gross Fixed Capital Formulation at time 't' (a proxy is used for capital);
- MIDDLE = Gross Enrollment in School at Middle level at time 't' (a proxy is used for human capital);
- OPEN = Openness (a measure of trade liberalization) at time 't';
- ψ_i = Coefficients are to be estimated; and
- ϵ_t = Error term assumed to be white noise.

Labor and capital are one of the essential drivers for economic growth. They play a vital role to boost economic activity. The proper amount of these two inputs make the economy vibrant and stable. Investments in capital goods (such as machinery, equipment, and technology) enhance the efficiency and output of the economy as well as increases employment opportunities, capacity, and the productivity of inputs that lead to economic growth. Population (POP) and Gross Fixed Capital Formulation (GFC) are used respectively as a proxy for labour and capital inputs.

Human capital is also very important determinant of economic growth because it determines the potential for future growth. A increased investment in human capital leads to greater economic growth. Investment in education is one of the indicators of human capital. Following Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1995) and Woller and Phillips (1998), gross enrolment in school at middle

level (MIDDLE) is used as a proxy for human capital.

Theoretical and empirical research suggests that trade liberalization has a strong and positive correlation with economic growth over a longer period. Jin (2000) argued that trade liberalization or openness is used to be an important and critical factor for economic activity. Whereas, Sachs and Warner (1995) are of the view that, "open economies has grown about 2.5% faster than closed economies and the difference is even larger among developing countries."¹⁴ Thus, a rise in openness (OPEN) is expected to have a positive impact on economic growth.

Empirical Model

Depending upon the order of integration, the present study adopts the recently new framework of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) framework developed by Pesaran and Shin (1999) and Pesaran et. al (2001) for the determination of long-run relationships between two variables of interest. This approach has advantages over the previous conventional techniques of Johansen (1998). The conventional technique requires that all system variables are integrated of order 1. This new technique is applicable to test the co-integration at levels irrespective whether the underlying regressors are purely I(0) or I(1) or a mixture of both. In the case of having I(2) variables in the model, the ARDL technique crashes and it yields spurious results. According to Ouattara (2004), if variables are I(2), the computed F-statistics are not valid and the estimated results are spurious because the bound testing approach is based on the assumption that the variables are either I(0) or I(1) not I(2). Finally, this new technique could be used with a limited number of observations (30 observations to 80 observations).

With respect to Equation (2) it is assumed that there is a long-run relationship among GDP, FD, POP, GFC, MIDDLE, and OPEN. As the direction of long-run relationship among the variables is unknown a priori, the following unrestricted error correction model can be regressed for the determination of a long-run relationship:

Where 'Δ' is first difference operator, 'i' are the number of lags, 'n' are the optimal lags length that can be selected by either Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC) or Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) before the given

$$\Delta \ln(Y)_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \Delta \ln(Y)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i \Delta \ln(\text{FD})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_i \Delta \ln(\text{POP})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \theta_i \Delta \ln(\text{GFC})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i \Delta \ln(\text{MIDDLE})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \pi_i \Delta \ln(\text{OPEN})_{t-i} + \psi_1 \ln(Y)_{t-1} + \psi_2 \ln(\text{FD})_{t-1} + \psi_3 \ln(\text{POP})_{t-1} + \psi_4 \ln(\text{GFC})_{t-1} + \psi_5 \ln(\text{MIDDLE})_{t-1} + \psi_6 \ln(\text{OPEN})_{t-1} + v_t \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

model is estimated by OLS and v_t is the error term. However, given the limited number of observations (38) and use of annual data, following Pesaran and Shin (1999), the lag length is restricted to two (i.e. n=2).

The F-test is used to validate a long-run relationship. The null hypothesis for a no long-run relationship among the variables in equation (3) is (H₀: $\psi_1 = \psi_2 = \psi_3 = \psi_4 = \psi_5 = \psi_6 = 0$) against the alternative hypothesis (H₁: $\psi_1 \neq \psi_2 \neq \psi_3 \neq \psi_4 \neq \psi_5 \neq \psi_6 \neq 0$). Two critical values [I(0) and I(1)] are taken from Pesaran (2001). The value I(0) shows the lower bound while I(1) represent the upper bound. If computed F-statistics is greater than upper bound, the null hypothesis of a no long-run relationship can be rejected. Conversely, if the computed value of F-statistics is lower than the lower bound, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Finally, if computed F-statistics fall between lower and upper bounds, the results are inconclusive.

Once the long-run relationship is established using equation (3) and following the above procedure, the long-run model can be estimated as follows:

$$\ln(Y)_t = \Omega_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \Omega_1 \ln(Y)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Omega_2 \ln(\text{FD})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Omega_3 \ln(\text{POP})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Omega_4 \ln(\text{GFC})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Omega_5 \ln(\text{MIDDLE})_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Omega_6 \ln(\text{OPEN})_{t-i} + v_t \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where, all variables are as previously defined and 'i' represents the optimal number of lags that can be selected by using either AIC or SBC criteria. After the estimation of the long-run model, the short-run dynamic parameters can be obtained through the estimation of the following error-correction model associated with long-run elasticities:

Where $\Pi_i, \Theta_i, \Omega_i, \Psi_i, \Gamma_i,$ and Φ_i are coefficients of short-run dynamic parameters and λ captures the speed of adjustment and signifies how much of the

$$\Delta \ln(Y)_t = \rho_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \Pi_i \Delta \ln(Y)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Theta_i \Delta \ln(FD)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Omega_i \Delta \ln(POP)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Psi_i \Delta \ln(GFC)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Gamma_i \Delta \ln(MIDDLE)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_i \Delta \ln(OPEN)_{t-i} + \lambda ECT_{t-1} + v_t \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

adjustment to equilibrium takes place each period or how much of the equilibrium error is corrected.

The annual data for the period of 1972-2009 is used for empirical analysis. Data on GDP at market price is taken from *Pakistan Economic Survey* various issue and is divided by the Consumer Price Index to make the data real. The real GDP is used as a proxy for economic growth mainly for the reasons that it is easy to measure and interpret than other economic performance indicators; in addition, data on this variable is readily available.

Data on FD, POP, GFC and MIDDLE are obtained from the *Handbook of Statistics on Pakistan Economy 2005* up to year 2005 while the data on remaining years are obtained from *Pakistan Economic Survey 2009-10*. Openness is defined as the total volume of foreign trade (sum of export and import) as a percentage of GDP and data is taken from the Penn World Table.

Empirical Results

Prior to testing the long-run relationship between variables of interest, using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) technique, a unit root test is conducted for each variable to check the order of integration. Even though ARDL does not require the pre-testing of a variable, the unit root test is conducted to convince us whether or not the ARDL technique can be used. The test results confirm the complex nature of dynamic properties of variables, with a mixture of I(0) and I(1) series suitable for ARDL techniques.

In ARDL analysis, the first step is to determine the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables. For this purposes, equation (3) is estimated. Following Pesaran and Shin (1999), the maximum two orders of lag are used in the estimation. F-statistics are computed through a Wald test wherein coefficients of long-run variables are restricted (i.e. $\psi_1 = \psi_2 = \psi_3 = \psi_4 = \psi_5 = \psi_6 = 0$). The computed F-statistics together with critical values computed by Pesaran et.al (2001) (Table

2). The computed F-statistics (3.776) are higher than the upper bound critical value at a 10% significance level (3.59), using unrestricted intercept and unrestricted trends.¹⁵ This implies that the null hypothesis of a non-existence of a long-run relationship can be rejected. Thus, it establishes that there is a long run relationship among the variables.

Table 2. Testing For the Existence of Long-Run Relationship

Computed F-statistics Value	Level of Significance	Critical Values (unrestricted intercept and unrestricted trends)	
		I(0)	I(1)
3.776	1%	3.60	4.90
	5%	2.87	4.00
	10%	2.53	3.59

Source: critical values are obtained from Pesaran et.al (2001)

After the establishment of the long run relationship, coefficients of the long-run model (Equation 4) are estimated. The optimal lags are selected based on AIC criteria. The estimated results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Long-Run Model[Dependent Variable: ln (Y)]
ARDL (1,0,0,1,2,1) is selected on the basis of AIC criteria

Variables ¹⁶	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-Statistics	p-value
ln (Y) _{t-1}	0.494*	0.144	3.421	0.002
ln (FD) _t	0.077***	0.041	1.873	0.072
ln (POP) _t	0.871**	0.356	2.445	0.021
ln (GFC) _{t-1}	0.103*	0.025	4.058	0.000
ln (MIDDLE) _{t-2}	-0.129*	0.039	-3.287	0.003
ln (OPEN) _{t-1}	-0.101**	0.049	-2.073	0.048
Constant	1.989**	0.578	3.440	0.002
Trend	0.011**	0.004	2.712	0.011

R-squared 0.999 S.E. Reg. 0.022

Adjusted R-squared 0.998 No. of Obs. 36

* , ** , *** represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations based on E-Views 5

The estimated coefficients of a long-run relationship show that FD has a positive and significant impact on output that is significant at 10%. The result is inline with our expectation and the findings of Lin and Liu (2000), Behnisch et. al (2001), and Malik et. al (2006). The

magnitude of its coefficient shows that *ceteris paribus*, if 1% autonomy in expenditure is given to the provinces, it will raise the output by more than 0.07%. The statistical significance of this variable supported the theoretical linkages of FD with economic growth. The positive relation implies that society has started to receive a benefit from the decentralization policy. The sign of the population is positive and significant at conventional 5% level of significance. The results suggest that *ceteris paribus*, a 1% increase in population size leads to a more than 0.87% rise in output level. Gross fixed capital formulation is significant at 1% and has a positive impact on economic growth. The human capital proxied by gross enrollment in school at the middle level has a significant but negative impact on economic growth. The apparent negative impact of human capital on output may be due to measurement inaccuracies. The possible implication for this negative sign might be that knowledge imparted during the school is insufficient to make the labor force productive. Openness is statistically significant at 5% but appears with a negative sign. This implies that the Pakistani economy is specializing in sectors that have a comparative disadvantage in the long-run. The economy specializes in traditional goods and the experience is a reduction in long-run economic growth.

The results of the short-run dynamics associated with the long-run elasticities estimated from Equation 5 are reported in Table 4. The sign of short-run dynamic impacts are maintained in the long-run except the openness variable that has now changed to positive. However, when the short-run model is estimated based on the long-run relationship, all control variables become insignificant at the conventional levels of significance. This is inline with modern growth theories that argued that differenced variables become insignificant under a steady state of growth in the short-run.

The coefficient of Error Correction term (ECT_{t-1}) measures the speed of adjustment towards the long-run equilibrium. It is significant at 10% and has a correct sign that ensures that the long-run equilibrium can be attained. The magnitude of its coefficient shows that approximately 56% of disequilibria from the previous year's shock converge back to the long-run equilibrium in the current year.

Table 4. Short Run Dynamics – Error Correction Model[Dependent Variable: $\Delta \ln(Y)$]

ARDL (1,0,0,1,2,1) is selected on the basis of AIC criteria

Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-Statistics	p-Value
$\Delta \ln(Y)_{t-1}$	0.217	0.289	0.753	0.459
$\Delta \ln(FD)_t$	0.124	0.040	3.098	0.005
$\Delta \ln(POP)_t$	0.106	0.136	0.776	0.445
$\Delta \ln(GFC)_{t-1}$	0.095	0.061	1.556	0.132
$\Delta \ln(MIDDLE)_{t-2}$	-0.053	0.042	-1.253	0.222
$\Delta \ln(OPEN)_{t-1}$	0.014	0.057	0.252	0.803
Constant	0.054	0.018	2.955	0.007
Trend	-0.001	0.000	-2.062	0.050
ECT_{t-1}	-0.560	0.323	-1.737	0.095
R-squared	0.368		S.E. Reg.	0.026
Adjusted R-squared	0.166		No. of Obs.	34

*, **, *** represent 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance respectively.

Source: Authors' estimations based on E-Views 5

The model passes the diagnostic tests for serial correlation, functional form misspecification, and the autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) test. The model also passes the Jarque-Bera normality test that implies that errors are normally distributed. The cumulative sum (CUSUM) and the cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMSQ) of a recursive residual test are also conducted to check the structural stability. The model looks stable and correctly specified as both CUSUM and CUSUMSQ test statistics are within the bounds of a 5% level of significance (Figure 2 and 3 respectively).

Figure 2: Cumulative Sum of Recursive Residual

Figure 3: Cumulative Sum of Square of Recursive Residual

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The present study examined the experience of Pakistan in the devolution of fiscal powers to lower tiers of government and determined their impact on economic growth. It analyzed efforts of political and military governments to accelerate the process of decentralization in Pakistan. In terms of fiscal status, it may be concluded that the public finances of Pakistan have the following characteristics: poor revenue mobilization, persistent fiscal deficit, high vertical imbalances between federal and provinces, a highly skewed expenditure structure, and weak financial management.

This study used a newly developed techniques of ARDL for the determination of the long-run relationship between FD and economic growth. Following the literature, an expenditure approach is used to measure the degree of FD. Under this approach FD is defined as a share of consolidated provincial government expenditures in total government expenditures net of intergovernmental transfers; in addition, real GDP is used as a proxy for economic growth. After controlling the effect of growth that includes other variables into the model, the ARDL technique is used to examine the long-run relationship. It established the long-run relationship among the variables of interest. The findings of the study imply that the over dependence of provincial governments on centre, undefined functional and tax responsibilities as well as a limited and unaffected tax base for provincial and local governments undermine the full benefits of FD.

The present study offers several policy implications.

First, under the condition that the explicit aim of policy makers is to induce economic performance through the enhancement of efficiency and accountability in public resources, the results of present study suggest that FD can be used as a tool for the accomplishment of this aim. Second, having its long-run association with economic growth, it provides an alternative policy option to achieve the aim of sustainable long-run economic growth. Third, the benefits of decentralization could be higher if the policy makers pay attention to the improvement of current socio-economic conditions, institutional mechanisms, and the legal system. Fourth, the study suggests that Pakistan should specialize in a sector where it has a comparative advantage and move from the trade of traditional sectors to value-added manufacturing sectors. Finally, the study suggests that policy makers should pay attention for the accumulation of human capital as it has a long-run relationship with economic growth.

NOTE

- [1] This article is derived from unpublished Master thesis submitted to the KDI School of Public Policy and Management, Korea as a partial fulfillment of degree requirement
- [2] As defined by Xie et. al (1999), p. 228
- [3] see Tanzi, (1995); Hemming and Spahn (1997); Leterlier (2003) for details.
- [4] Pakistan became from British in August, 1947.
- [5] i.e. General Ayub Khan regime (1958-1969), General Zia ul Haq regime (1978-1988) and General Pervez Musharraf regime (Oct. 1999 -Nov. 2007).
- [6] Pakistan has four provinces - Sindh, Punjab, Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa (former NWFP), and Baluchistan.
- [7] with political, administrative, and financial powers.
- [8] i.e. Baskaran and Feld (2009).
- [9] FD-Exp is defined as ratio of consolidated provincial expenditure in the total expenditure net of intergovernmental transfers where total expenditures are a sum of federal and consolidated provincial expenditures.
- [10] FD-Rev is a revenue approach measure and defined as a ratio of consolidated provincial revenue to total revenue, net of inter-governmental transfers.
- [11] General Musharraf resigned from the Presidency on November 2007 and a democratic government took charge after election in February 2008.
- [12] See Oates (1995); Davoodi and Zou (1998); Zhong and

Zou (1998); Xie, et. al (1999) for details.

[13] See Woller and Phillips (1998) for details.

[14] cited in Mohammad (2010), p. 422.

[15] The other possibilities as proposed by Pesaran et. al (2001) such as unrestricted intercept and restricted trends were also checked; however, the result rinsing netiquette.

[16] Beside these variables, other variables such as Labor Force, Market Capitalization, External Debt, Inflation Rate, and Fiscal Deficit have a possible influence on economic growth and were also included in the model; however, the results were insignificant.

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